

The Advantage of Regularizing a Specific Elliptical Problem by the Truncation and Mollification Methods

YAMEOGO Pierre Claver
Dr. En Mathématiques (Ph.D)

Abstract:- The try to prove the importance and advantage of using the truncation method and the mollification method to regularize an ill-posed elliptical problem. To find appropriate solutions, we will try to calculate the difference between the original solution and the approximate solution. We give a concrete example to see how to apply the theoretical results developed in this search.

I. INTRODUCTION

We propose two spectral regularization methods to construct an approximate stable solution to our original problem.

Finally, some other convergence results including some explicit convergence rates are also established under a priori bound assumptions on the exact solution. But other methods can be used in our case here. The complexity of studying a poorly posed problem requires mastery of certain concepts, especially in elliptical case.

II. REGULARIZATION AND ERROR ESTIMATES

➤ *The Truncation Method.*

From

$$u(y) = U(y) + W(y) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} (e^{y\sqrt{\lambda}} + e^{-y\sqrt{\lambda}}) dE_{\lambda} f. \quad (1'')$$

We can see that the term $e^{y\sqrt{\lambda}}$ is the cause of instability. In order to overcome the ill-posedness of problem:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{yy}(y) &= Au(y), & 0 < y < L, \\ u(0) &= f, & \\ u_y(0) &= 0, & \end{aligned} \quad (1')$$

we modify the solution by filtering the high frequencies using a suitable method and instead consider (1'') only for $\lambda \leq \beta(\delta)$, where $\beta(\delta)$ is some constant which satisfies $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \beta(\delta) = +\infty$.

According to spectral theory of self-adjoint operators [20], for any bounded Borel set, $\Delta_{\beta} = \{\gamma \leq t \leq \beta\} \subseteq \sigma(A) = [\gamma, +\infty[$, we can define the orthogonal projection

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1}_{\Delta_{\beta}} &= \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} \mathbf{1}_{\Delta_{\beta}}(\lambda) dE_{\lambda} = E_{\beta}, & (1) \\ \forall h \in H, & \quad h_{\beta} = E_{\beta} h \rightarrow h, \quad \beta \rightarrow +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

To solve (1) in a stable way we approximate f by its projection f_{β} , and instead of considering (1) with f we take its projected version

$$\begin{aligned} u_{\beta}(x) &= \cosh(y\sqrt{A}) f_{\beta} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} (e^{y\sqrt{\lambda}} + e^{-y\sqrt{\lambda}}) \mathbf{1}_{[\gamma, \beta]} dE_{\lambda} f, & (2) \end{aligned}$$

Where $\mathbf{1}_{[a,b]}$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[a,b]$ for $a < b$. The quantity β is referred to as a cut-off frequency. Let f (resp., f_{δ}) be the exact (resp., the measured data) at $y=0$, such that $\|f - f_{\delta}\| \leq \delta$.

Abstract and applied Analysis.

The approximated solution v_{β}^{δ} corresponding to the measured data f_{δ} is denoted by

$$v_{\beta}^{\delta}(y) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} (e^{y\sqrt{\lambda}} + e^{-y\sqrt{\lambda}}) \mathbf{1}_{[\gamma, \beta]} dE_{\lambda} f_{\delta}. \quad (3)$$

For simplicity, we denote the solution of problem (1') by $u(y)$, and the regularized solution associated to the data f_{δ} by $v_{\beta}^{\delta}(y)$.

Our first main theorem is the following theorem.

➤ *Theorem 1.* The solution defined in (2) depends continuously in $\mathbf{C}([0, L], H)$ on the data f ; that is, if u_{β}^1 and u_{β}^2 are two regularized solutions corresponding to f_1 and f_2 , respectively, then on has

$$\|u_{\beta}^1(y) - u_{\beta}^2(y)\| \leq e^{y\sqrt{\beta}} \|f_1 - f_2\|. \quad (4)$$

This inequality implies that the solution of the regularized problem (2) depends continuously on the data f .

Now we compute the difference between the original solution $u = u(y; f)$ and the approximate solution $v_{\beta}^{\delta} = v_{\beta}^{\delta}(y; f_{\delta})$.

➤ *Theorem 2.* Let $u \in C([0; L]; H)$ be a solution problem (1') with the exact data $f \in H$; then the following estimate holds:

$$\|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\| \leq \frac{2}{e^{(L-y)\sqrt{\beta}}} \|u(L)\|. \quad (5)$$

Proof. From relations (1'') and (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned} u(y) - u_\beta(t) &= \int_\beta^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) dE_\lambda f \quad (6) \\ &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty]} dE_\lambda f \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} &u(y) - u_\beta(y) \\ &= \int_\lambda^{+\infty} \frac{\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda})}{\cosh(L\sqrt{\lambda})} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty]} \cosh(L\sqrt{\lambda}) dE_\lambda f, \\ &\|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\|^2 \\ &\leq \int_\lambda^{+\infty} \left(\frac{\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda})}{\cosh(L\sqrt{\lambda})} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty]} \right)^2 \cosh(L\sqrt{\lambda})^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2. \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Using the inequality

$$\left(\frac{\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda})}{\cosh(L\sqrt{\lambda})} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty]} \right)^2 \leq \frac{4}{e^{2(L-y)\sqrt{\beta}}}$$

$$\int_\beta^{+\infty} \cosh^2(L\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \leq \|u(L)\|^2, \quad (8)$$

Abstract and Applied Analysis

We derive

$$\|u(y)\|^2 \leq \frac{4}{e^{2(L-y)\sqrt{\beta}}} \|u(L)\|^2. \quad (9)$$

Using (4), (5) and the triangle inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \\ &\leq \|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\| + \|u_\beta(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \quad (10) \\ &\leq \frac{2}{e^{(L-y)\sqrt{\beta}}} \|u(L)\| + e^{y\sqrt{\beta}} \delta. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

➤ *Remark 1.* If we choose $\sqrt{\beta} = (1/L)\log(M/\delta)$, where $\|u(L)\| = M$, then we have the error bound

$$\|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \leq 3M^{(L-y)/L} \delta^{y/L}. \quad (11)$$

From (11) we see that (3) is an approximation of the exact solution $u(y)$. The approximation error depends continuously on the measurement error for fixed $0 < y < L$.

However, as $y \rightarrow L$, the accuracy of the regularized solution becomes progressively lower. Consequently, we

have note any information about the continuous dependence of the solution if y is close to L .

In the theory of ill-posed Cauchy problems, we can often obtain continuous dependence on the data for the closed interval $[0, L]$ by assuming additional smoothness and using a stronger norm.

Now we show two error estimates under the following conditions:

$$(H1) u(L) \in D(A^p),$$

$$(H2) u(L) \in G_p, p > 0.$$

➤ *Remark 2.* In practice, we know that it is very difficult to verify the conditions (H1) and (H2), so we give different assumptions on the given data f as follows:

$$u(L) \in D(A^p) \Leftrightarrow \int_Y^{+\infty} \lambda^{2p} \cosh^2(L\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < \infty$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \int_Y^{+\infty} \lambda^{2p} e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < \infty,$$

$$u(L) \in G_p \Leftrightarrow \int_Y^{+\infty} \lambda^{2pL\sqrt{\lambda}} \cosh^2(L\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < \infty$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \int_Y^{+\infty} e^{2(1+p)L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < \infty,$$

$$\Leftrightarrow f \in G_{p+1}. \quad (12)$$

➤ *Theorem 3* If

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_Y^{+\infty} \lambda^p e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < E_1^2 \quad (\text{resp.}, \\ &\int_Y^{+\infty} e^{2(1+q)L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < E_2^2), p > 0, q > 0, \end{aligned}$$

then one has the following estimates:

$$\begin{aligned} &\|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{a}\right)^p E_1 \log\left(\frac{1}{\delta}\right)^{-p} + \delta^{1-\frac{ya}{L}}, \quad 0 < a \leq 1, \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

$$\|u(y) - v_\beta(y)\| \leq e^{-q\sqrt{\beta}} E_2 + e^{y\sqrt{\beta}} \delta.$$

Proof. From the expansions

$$\begin{aligned} u(y) &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) dE_\lambda f, \\ u_\beta(y) &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) \mathbf{1}_{[Y, \beta]} dE_\lambda f, \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$u(y) - u_\beta(y) = \int_Y^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty)} dE_\lambda f. \tag{15}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\|^2 \\ &= \int_Y^{+\infty} (\lambda^{-p/2} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty)})^2 \cosh^2(y\sqrt{\lambda}) \lambda^p d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \int_Y^{+\infty} (\lambda^{-p/2} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty)})^2 \cosh^{2e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} \lambda^p} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \tag{16} \\ &\leq \beta^{-p} \int_Y^{+\infty} e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} \lambda^p d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \sqrt{\beta}^{-2p} E_1^2. \end{aligned}$$

Using theorem 3 and the triangle inequality, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \\ &\leq \|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\| + \|u_\beta(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \tag{17} \\ &\leq \sqrt{\beta}^{-p} E_1 + e^{y\sqrt{\beta}} \delta. \end{aligned}$$

By choosing, $\sqrt{\beta} = (a/L) \log(1/\delta)$, we obtain the desired inequality.

Using the same techniques, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & u(y) - u_\beta(y) \\ &= \int_Y^\infty e^{-q\sqrt{\lambda}} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) e^{q\sqrt{\lambda}} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty)} dE_\lambda f, \tag{18} \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\|^2 \\ &= \int_Y^\infty (e^{-q\sqrt{\lambda}} \mathbf{1}_{[\beta, +\infty)})^2 (\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) e^{2q\sqrt{\lambda}})^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq e^{-2q\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda u(y)\|^2 \leq e^{-2q\sqrt{\beta}} E_2^2 \tag{19} \end{aligned}$$

Using (4) and the triangle inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \\ &\leq \|u(y) - u_\beta(y)\| + \|u_\beta(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \tag{20} \\ &\leq e^{-q\sqrt{\beta}} E_2 + e^{y\sqrt{\beta}} \delta. \end{aligned}$$

By choosing, $\sqrt{\beta} = (a/L) \log(1/\delta)$, we obtain

$$\|u(y) - v_\beta^\delta(y)\| \leq \delta^{aq/L} E_2 + \delta^{1-ay/L} \tag{21}$$

➤ *The Mollification Method.* Now, we approximate the original problem (1) by the sequence of problems

$$\begin{aligned} & u_{yy} = Au, \quad 0 < y < L, \\ & u(0) = f_\alpha = M_\alpha f, \tag{22} \\ & u_y(0) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

➤ *Theorem 4.* If $f \in H$ the approximate Cauchy problem (22) admits a unique solution u_α , which depends continuously upon the data f with respect to uniform topology of $C([0, L]; H)$.

Proof. From the representation

$$\begin{aligned} & u_\alpha(y) = \cosh(y\sqrt{A}) f_\alpha \\ &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda}) (1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}})^{-1} dE_\lambda f, \tag{23} \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u_\alpha(y)\|^2 = \int_Y^{+\infty} \left\{ \frac{\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda})}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\}^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \int_Y^{+\infty} \left\{ \frac{e^{L\sqrt{\lambda}}}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\}^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2. \tag{24} \end{aligned}$$

• If $p = 1$, we obtain

$$\sup_{y \in [0, L]} \|u_\alpha(y)\|^2 \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \|f\|. \tag{25}$$

• If $p > 1$, the function $M(s) = e^{Ls} / (1 + \alpha e^{pLs})$ with $s = \sqrt{\lambda} \geq \sqrt{\gamma}$ achieves its maximum at $s^* = (1/pL) \log(1/\alpha(p-1))$, $p > 1$, from which we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} & M_\infty = M(s^*) = c(p) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{1/p}, \tag{26} \\ & c(p) = p^{-1}(p-1)^{1-1/p} \leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

From this bound, we drive

$$\sup_{y \in [0, L]} \|u_\alpha(y)\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|f\|. \tag{27}$$

From the linear property of our problem, stability estimate of problem (22) may be written precisely in the following corollary.

➤ *Corollary 1.* If $u_{\alpha,1}(y; f_1)$ (resp. $u_{\alpha,2}(y, f_2)$) is the approximate solution corresponding to f_1 (resp. f_2), then

$$\sup_{y \in [0, L]} \|u_{\alpha,1}(y) - u_{\alpha,2}(y)\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|f_1 - f_2\| \quad (28)$$

➤ *Remark 3.* We have

$$\begin{aligned} N(s) &= \frac{s^r e^{Ts}}{1 + \alpha e^{pTs}} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} k(s) \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} s^r e^{-(p-1)Ts}, \quad p > 1, \\ s &= \sqrt{\lambda} \geq \sqrt{\gamma}. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

It is easy to show that

$$\begin{aligned} K(s) &\leq K\left(s^* = \frac{r}{L(p-1)}\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{r}{L(p-1)}\right)^r e^{-r} = k(r, p, L) < \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

This remark shows that $u_\alpha(y) \in D(A^{r/2})$ for all $y \in [0, L]$.

Proof. The inclusion $u_\alpha(y) \in D(A^{r/2})$ is equivalent to $\|A^{r/2}u_\alpha(y)\| < \infty$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \|A^{r/2}u_\alpha(y)\|^2 &= \int_\gamma^{+\infty} \lambda^r \left\{ \frac{\cosh(y\sqrt{\lambda})}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\}^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^2 \int_\gamma^{+\infty} \{\sqrt{\lambda}^r e^{-(p-1)L\sqrt{\lambda}}\}^2 d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^2 k(r, p, L)^2 \|f\|^2 < \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Where $k(r, p, L) = \sup_{\lambda \geq \gamma} \sqrt{\lambda}^r e^{-(p-1)L\sqrt{\lambda}} = \left(\frac{r}{(p-1)L}\right)^r e^{-r}$.

Abstract and Applied Analysis

➤ *Theorem 5.* If $f \in G_1$, then

$$\sup_{y \in [0, L]} \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\| \rightarrow 0, \quad \alpha \rightarrow 0. \quad (32)$$

Proof. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\|^2 &= \int_\gamma^{+\infty} (1 - M_\alpha(\lambda))^2 \cosh^2(y\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \int_\gamma^{+\infty} (1 - M_\alpha(\lambda))^2 \cosh^2(L\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \int_\gamma^{+\infty} (1 - M_\alpha(\lambda))^2 e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} (y\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &= \|(I - M_\alpha)\hat{f}\|^2, \end{aligned}$$

Where $\hat{f} = e^{L\sqrt{\lambda}} f$ and $\|\hat{f}\|^2 = \int_\gamma^{+\infty} e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 < \infty$.

This implies that $\sup_{y \in [0, L]} \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\| \leq \|(I - M_\alpha)\hat{f}\|$

And by virtue of (1) of theorem, we conclude the desired convergence.

The following technical lemmas play the key role in our analysis and calculations.

➤ *Lemma 1.* Let

$$\begin{aligned} [v, +\infty[\ni s \rightarrow Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) \\ = \frac{1}{\alpha s^r + a e^{-qLs}}, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Where $a > 0, \alpha > 0, v > 0, q > 0, L > 0$, and $r \geq 1$. Then one has

$$Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{k_1}{\log(k_2(1/\alpha))}\right)^r, \quad (35)$$

Where $k_1(r, q, L) = r q L, k_2(q, r, L, a) = q^r L^{r-1} a / r$.

Proof. Differentiating the expression and setting the derivative equal to zero, we find

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{d}{ds} Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) \\ &= \frac{-1}{(\alpha s^r + a e^{-qLs})^2} (\alpha r s^{r-1} - q a e^{-qLs}) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The function $(d/ds) Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) = 0$ admits a unique solution

$$s = \{s \mapsto \alpha r s^{r-1}\} \cap \{s \mapsto q a e^{-qLs}\}. \quad (37)$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) &\leq Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; \hat{s}) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\alpha \hat{s}^r + a e^{-qL\hat{s}}} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha \hat{s}^r}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

We have

$$(\alpha r \hat{s}^{r-1} - q a e^{-qL\hat{s}}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow s^{r-1} e^{qL\hat{s}} = \frac{q a}{r \alpha}. \quad (39)$$

By using the inequality ($e^t \geq t, t \geq 0$), then for $t = qL\hat{s}$, we obtain $e^{qL\hat{s}} \geq qL\hat{s}$ and we can write

$$\frac{q^a}{r\alpha} = \hat{s}^{r-1} e^{qL\hat{s}} \leq e^{qL\hat{s}} \left(\frac{e^{qL\hat{s}}}{qL}\right)^{r-1} = \left(\frac{1}{qL}\right)^{r-1} e^{r qL\hat{s}}, \quad (40)$$

Which implies that

$$\geq \left(\frac{1}{rqL}\right) \log\left(\left(\frac{q^{rLr^{-1}a}}{r}\right)\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)\right). \text{Hense, we obtain}$$

$$Q(\{a, r, q, L\}; s) \leq \frac{1}{\alpha \hat{s}^r} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{k_1}{\log\left(k_2\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)\right)}\right)^r, \quad (41)$$

Where $k_1(r, q, L) = rqL, k_2(q, r, L, a) = q^r L^{r-1} a/r$.

➤ Lemma 2. Let

$$[v, +\infty[\ni s \mapsto R(\{p, q, L\}; s) = \frac{e^{pLs}}{(1 + \alpha e^{pLs})e^{qLs}} = \frac{1}{e^{(q-p)Ls} + \alpha e^{qLs}}, \quad (42)$$

Where $p \geq 1, q > 0, \alpha > 0, v > 0$, and $L > 0$. Then on has the following.

If $1 \leq p \leq q$, then

$$R(\{p, q, L\}; s) \leq e^{-(q-p)Ls} \leq e^{-(q-p)Lv} \leq 1. \quad (43)$$

If $0 < q < p, p \geq 1, 0 < \alpha \leq (p - q)/q$, then

$$R(\{p, q, L\}; s) \leq k_3 \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{(p-q)/p}$$

$$k_3(p, q) = \frac{q}{p} \left(\frac{p - q}{p}\right)^{(p-q)/p} \leq 1. \quad (44)$$

Proof. By a simple differential calculus, we show that the function $R(\{p, q, L\}; s)$

achieves its maximum at $\hat{s} = (1/pL) \log((p - q)/\alpha q)$. Consequently

$$R(\{p, q, L\}; s) \leq R(\{p, q, L\}; \hat{s}) = k_3 \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{(p-q)/p}. \quad (45)$$

Now we assume the following a priori bounds hold:

$$u(L) \in D(A^{r/2})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} \sqrt{\lambda}^{2r} e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_{\lambda} f\|^2 \leq E_1^2 < \infty, \quad (46)$$

$$u(L) \in G_q$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \int_{\gamma}^{+\infty} \sqrt{\lambda}^{2r} e^{2(1+q)\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_{\lambda} f\|^2 \leq E_1^2 < \infty. \quad (47)$$

➤ Theorem 6. Let

u (resp., u_{α}) be the solution of problem (1'') (resp., (22))

With the exact data f . If (46) (resp., (47)) is satisfied, then on has the

Following error estimates:

$$\|u(y) - u_{\alpha}(y)\| = 0 \left(\frac{1}{\log(1/\alpha)}\right)^r, \quad (48)$$

$$\|u(y) - u_{\alpha}(y)\| = \begin{cases} 0(\alpha), & \text{if } 1 \leq p \leq q, \\ 0(\alpha^{q/p}), & \text{if } 0 < q < p, p \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (49)$$

Proof. Putting

$$\begin{aligned} B_1(\lambda) &= \left\{ \frac{e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}^r} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}^r e^{-pL\sqrt{\lambda}} + \alpha \sqrt{\lambda}^r} \leq B_2(\lambda) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}^r e^{-pL\sqrt{\lambda}} + \alpha \sqrt{\lambda}^r}, \\ B_3(\lambda) &= \left\{ \frac{e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\} \frac{1}{e^{qL\sqrt{\lambda}}} = \frac{1}{e^{(q-p)L\sqrt{\lambda}} + \alpha e^{qL\sqrt{\lambda}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the change of variable, $s = \sqrt{\lambda}$, we obtain the new expressions

$$\hat{B}_2(s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}^r e^{-pLs} + \alpha e^r}, \quad (51)$$

$$\hat{B}_3(s) = \frac{1}{e^{(q-p)Ls} + \alpha e^{qLs}}. \quad (52)$$

By virtue of lemma 1 (inequality (35) and Lemma 2 (inequalities (43))

And (69)), we can write

$$\hat{B}_2(s) \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{k_1}{\log\left(k_2\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)\right)}\right)^r, \quad (53)$$

Where $k_1(r, p, L) = rqL, k_2(p, r, L, \sqrt{\gamma}^r) = q^r, L^{r-1} \sqrt{\gamma}^{r/r}$. Consider

$$\widehat{B}_3(s) \leq \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq p \leq q, \\ \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{(p-q)/p}, & \text{if } 0 < q < p, p \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (54)$$

Abstract and Applied Analysis

We Have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\|^2 \\ &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \left\{ \frac{\alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\}^2 \cosh^2(y\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \alpha^2 \int_Y^{+\infty} \{B_2(\lambda)\}^2 \sqrt{\lambda}^{-2r} e^{2L\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \alpha^2 \left(\sup_{s \geq \sqrt{Y}} \widehat{B}_2(s) \right)^2 E_1^2, \quad (55) \\ & \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\|^2 \\ &= \int_Y^{+\infty} \left\{ \frac{\alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}}{1 + \alpha e^{pL\sqrt{\lambda}}} \right\}^2 \cosh^2(y\sqrt{\lambda}) d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \alpha^2 \int_Y^{+\infty} \{B_3(\lambda)\}^2 e^{L(1+q)\sqrt{\lambda}} d\|E_\lambda f\|^2 \\ &\leq \alpha^2 \left(\sup_{s \geq \sqrt{Y}} \widehat{B}_2(s) \right)^2 E_2^2. \end{aligned}$$

Using (53) and (54), we drive

$$\begin{aligned} \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\|^2 &\leq \alpha \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{k_1}{\log\left(k_2 \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)\right)} \right)^r \\ &= 0 \left(\frac{1}{\log(k_2(1/\alpha))} \right)^r, \\ \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\|^2 &\leq \begin{cases} \alpha, & \text{if } 1 \leq p \leq q, \\ \alpha^{q/p}, & \text{if } 0 < q < p, p \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (56) \end{aligned}$$

Combining (28), (48), and (49) with the help of triangle inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u(y) - u_\alpha^\delta(y)\| \\ &\leq \|u(y) - u_\alpha(y)\| \quad (57) \\ &+ \|u(y) - u_\alpha^\delta(y)\| = \Delta_1 + \Delta_2, \end{aligned}$$

We deduce the following corollary.

➤ *Corollary 3.* Let $u(y; f)$ (resp., $u_\alpha^\delta(y; f_\delta)$) be the solution of problem (1) (resp., (47)) with the exact data

f (resp., the inexact data f_δ) such that $\|f - f_\delta\| \leq \delta$. If (46) (resp., (47)) is satisfied, then one has the following error estimates:

(case $r \geq 1$)

$$\|u(y) - u_\alpha^\delta(y)\| = 0(\theta_1(\alpha)) + \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{1/p} \delta, \quad (58)$$

Abstract and applied Analysis

(Case $1 \leq p \leq q$)

$$\|u(y) - u_\alpha^\delta(y)\| = 0(\theta_1(\alpha)) + \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{1/p} \delta, \quad (59)$$

(Case $0 < q < p, p \geq 1$)

$$\|u(y) - u_\alpha^\delta(y)\| = 0(\theta_3(\alpha)) + \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^{1/p} \delta, \quad (60)$$

Where

$$\theta_1(\alpha) = 0 \left(\frac{1}{\log(1/\alpha)} \right)^r, \quad (61)$$

$$\theta_2(\alpha) = 0(\alpha), \quad \theta_3(\alpha) = 0(\alpha^{q/p}).$$

If we choose $\alpha = \alpha(\delta) = \delta^{p/\omega}$ with $\omega > 1$, then we have

$$\delta \left(\frac{1}{\delta^{p/\omega}} \right)^{1/p} = \delta^{(\omega-1)/\omega}, \quad (62)$$

$$\theta_1(\alpha) = 0 \left(\frac{1}{\log(1/\delta^{p/\omega})} \right)^r, \quad (63)$$

$$\theta_2(\alpha) = \delta^{p/\omega}, \quad \theta_3(\alpha) = 0(\alpha^{q/\omega}). \quad (64)$$

➤ *Example: Cauchy Problem for the Modified Helmholtz equation.*

In this paragraph, we give a concrete example to see how to apply the theoretical results developed in this Study.

Let us consider the Cauchy problem (modified Helmholtz equation) in the infinite strip $\mathbb{R} \times (0, 1)$

$$u_{yy}(x, y) + u_{xx}(x, y) - yu(x, y) = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad y \in (0, 1), \quad (65)$$

$$u(x, 0) = f(x), \quad u_y(x, 0) = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R},$$

Where y is a real positive constant

Let $\hat{u}(\xi, y) = (\mathcal{F}u)(\xi, y)$ be the Fourier transform of $u(x, y)$:

$$\hat{u}(\xi, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{\xi x} u(x, y) dx. \quad (66)$$

With the help of the Fourier transformed, problem (1'') can be transformed to an equivalent problem in the frequency domain:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_{yy}(\xi, y) - \xi^2 \hat{u}(\xi, y) - y \hat{u}(\xi, y) &= 0, \\ \xi \in \mathbb{R}, \quad y \in (0,1), \\ \hat{u}(\xi, 0) = \hat{f}(\xi), \hat{u}_y(\xi, 0) &= 0, \quad \xi \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check that the formal solution of problem (67) has the form

$$\hat{u}(\xi, y) = \cosh(y \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}) \hat{f}(\xi),$$

Or equivalently, the formal solution of problem (65) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y) &= (\mathcal{F}^{-1} \hat{u})(x, y) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{ix\xi} \hat{u}(\xi, y) d\xi \quad (69) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{ix\xi} \cosh(y \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}) \hat{f}(\xi) d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Putting $\Theta(\xi) = \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}$. Then $\Theta(\xi) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $|\xi| \rightarrow +\infty$. From this remark, it is easy to see that a small perturbation in data $\hat{f}(\xi)$ may cause a dramatically large error in the solution $\hat{u}(\xi, \xi)$. In addition, the magnifying factor is $\Theta(\xi) \sim e^{|\xi|}$, hence, the problem is severely ill-posed.

Since the data $f(\cdot)$ are based on (physical) observations and are not known with complete accuracy, we assume that f and f_δ satisfy

$$\|f - f_\delta\| \leq \delta, \quad (70)$$

Where f and f_δ belong to $L^2(\mathbb{R})$, f_δ denotes the measured data, and δ denotes the noise level.

For this problem, we define the regularized solutions with noisy data f_δ :

$$\begin{aligned} u_N^\delta(x, y) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{ix\xi} \cosh(y \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}) \hat{f}_\delta(\xi) \mathbf{1}_{[-N, N]}(\xi) d\xi \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-N}^N e^{ix\xi} \cosh(y \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}) \hat{f}_\delta(\xi) d\xi \quad (71) \end{aligned}$$

Where $\mathbf{1}_{[-N, N]}$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[-N, N]$

$$u_\alpha^\delta(x, y)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{ix\xi} \left(\frac{\cosh(y \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)})}{1 + \alpha e^{-p \sqrt{(\xi^2 + \gamma)}}} \right) \hat{f}_\delta(\xi) d\xi$$

Where $p \geq 1$. The quantities $\alpha = \alpha(\delta)$ and $N = N(\delta)$ are the parameters which were defined in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

III. CONCLUSION

We were able to solve the problem with the truncation method and the mollification method. Our goal will be devoted to problematic waters with unknown (uncertain) operators: Since the physical model proceeds from an idealization of physical reality and is based on simplifying assumptions, it is therefore also a source of uncertainty. Any regularization theory must therefore take into account the possibly incomplete for uncertain character. Also, we give some extensions to our investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1]. H. Brezis and A. Pazy. Convergence and approximation of Semigroups of Nonlinear Operators in Banach Spaces. *J. Func. Anal.*, 9:63-74, 1972.
- [2]. A.Tikhonov, V.Arsénine: Methods of regularization of Ill-posed problems. Ed 1976.
- [3]. D. D. Ang, R. Gorenflo, V. K .Le, and D. D. Trong, Moment Theory and Some Inverse Problems in Potential Theory and Heat Conduction, Vol. 1792 of Lecture Notes in Mathematics, Springer Berlin, Germany, 2002.
- [4]. A. M. Denisov, E. V. Zakharov, A. V. Kalinin and V. V. Kalinin, "Numerical solution of the inverse electrocardiography Problem With the use of the tikhonov regularization method," *Computational Mathematics and Cybernetics*, vol, 32, no. 2, pp. 61-68, 2008.
- [5]. M. M. Lavrentev, V. G. Romanov, and G. P. Shishatskii, *III- Posed Problems in Mathematical Physics and Analysis*, American Mathematical Society, RI, USA, 1986.
- [6]. L. E. Payne, *Improperly Posed Problems in Partial Differential Equations*, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, Philadelphia, Pa, USA, 1975.
- [7]. G. Alessandrini, L. Rondi, E. Rosset, and S. Vessella, "The Stability for the Cauchy problem for elliptic equations," *Inverse Problems*, vol. 25, no. 12, Article ID 123 004, 47 pages, 2009.
- [8]. U. Tautenhahn, "Optimal stable solution of Cauchy problems For elliptic equations," *Zeitschrift für Analysis und ihre Anwendungen*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 961-984, 1996.
- [9]. Z. Qian, C-L. Fu and Z-P. Li, "two regularization methods For a Cauchy problem for the Laplace equation," *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Application*, vol. 338, no. 1, pp.479 489, 2008.
- [10]. D. N. Hào, N. V. Duc, and D. Lesnic, "A non-local boundary Value problem method for the Cauchy problem for elliptic Equation," *Inverse problems*, vol. 25, no. 5, Article ID 055002, 27 pages, 2009.

- [11]. X-L. Feng, L. Eldén, and C.-L. Fu, "A quasi-boundary-value Method for the Cauchy problem for elliptic equations with Nonhomogeneous Neumann data," *Journal of Inverse and Ill-Posed Problems*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 617-645, 2010.
- [12]. I. V. Mel'nikova, "Regularization of ill-posed differential problems," *Siberian Mathematical Journal*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 289-298, 1992.
- [13]. P. N. Vabishchevich and A. Yu. Denisenko, "Regularization Of nonstationary problems for elliptic equations," *Journal of Engineering Physics and Thermophysics*, vol. 65, no. 6, pp. 1195-1199, 1993
- [14]. V. A. Kozlov and V.G. Maz'ya, "On iterative procedure for solving ill-posed boundary value problems that preserve differential Equations," *Leningrad Mathematical Journal*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 1207-1228, 1990.
- [15]. D. N. Hào, "A mollification method for ill-posed problems," *Numerische Mathematik*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 469-506, 1994.
- [16]. N. Dunford and J. Schwartz, *Linear Operators-Part II*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA, 1967
- [17]. A. Pazy, *Semigroups of Linear Operators and Applications to Partial Differential Equations*, vol. 44 of *Applied Mathematical Sciences*, Springer, New York, NY, USA, 1983.
- [18]. S. G. Krein and Ju. I. Petunin, "Scales of Banach spaces," *Uspekhi Matematicheskikh Nauk*, vol. 21, no. 2(128), pp. 89-168, 1966.
- [19]. H. O. Fattorini, *the Cauchy Problem*, vol. 18 of *Encyclopedia of Mathematics and Its Applications*, Addison-Wesley Publishing Reading, Mass, USA, 1983.
- [20]. K. Schmüdgen, *Unbounded Self-Adjoint Operators on Hilbert Space*, vol. 265 of *Graduate Texts in Mathematics*, Springer, Dordrecht The Netherlands, 2012.